

Autoregressive Behavior of Aviation Weather Forecasts

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We analyze U.S. Terminal Aerodrome Forecasts (TAFs) for autocorrelation of forecast changes for a given aerodrome and hour between successive forecasts. We find a pessimistic and overreacting bias. When forecasters adjust a TAF, they tend to back out some of their changes in a later TAF. This tendency is much more pronounced when forecasters worsen a forecast than when they improve it.

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Pilots rely on Terminal Aerodrome Forecasts or TAFs published typically every six hours for about 700 airports in the United States. (“Advisory Circular 00-45H: Aviation Weather Services” 2016; “Federal Meteorological Handbook Number 1: Surface Weather Observations and Reports” 2019) Although these forecasts rely on computer models, they still involve significant human judgment and are prepared by meteorologists. In the verbal discussions accompanying the formal forecasts, the meteorologists sometimes mention “not yet” including or changing something they foresee since there is not enough certainty yet.

We want to see if we can find evidence of the meteorologists being too conservative or too aggressive in incorporating new information as it becomes available. That is to say, we would like to see whether there is autoregressive behavior in changes of the forecast for the same parameter at the same time and place. Put simply, if the meteorologist makes his forecast worse than it was, is that reason to believe he will make it even worse in the next update? (*E.g.*, if in the evening before I want to go flying, the forecast for 9 AM the next morning goes from a cloud base of 5,000 ft to 4,000 ft, is that reason to assume that by the morning, the forecast will be 3,000 ft, in which case I’ll probably stay home?)

1 Research Problem

Research in psychology, financial markets, behavioral economics, and related fields has created an abundance of evidence that humans do not tend to update their forecasts of future events with optimal efficiency in the sense of a Bayesian update. However, the direction of these biases appears inconsistent. The literature provides ample evidence for humans being too conservative in their updates, *i.e.*, not taking new information fully into account, and well as for being too aggressive in their updates, with various explanations of both phenomena. (Edwards 1968; Griffin and Tversky 1992; Barberis, Shleifer, and Vishny 1998; Kahneman and Tversky 1973; De Bondt and Thaler 1985; Daniel, Hirshleifer, and Subrahmanyam 1998) We can define an efficient forecast as one that incorporates all information available when the forecast is made. (Nordhaus 1987; Coibion and Gorodnichenko 2012) If a forecast is efficient in this sense, there is no additional information to glean from looking at previous forecasts made for the same event by the same forecaster.

While forecast biases have often been discussed in the context of alleged irrationality by the forecasters, we should note that there are perfectly plausible rational reasons for making biased forecasts. Regarding weather forecasts for dissemination to the general public, there is a well-documented “wet bias” toward predicting rain. (Bickel and Kim 2008) This bias can be quite drastic, such as with predictions of a 20% chance of rain only materializing in about 5% of cases. (Silver 2012) One can easily hypothesize a plausible reason for such bias in what in quantitative finance would be called the pricing kernel, *i.e.*, an adjustment to weights in the probability space according to the unpleasantness of the event. Consumers of the weather report may be unhappier about getting wet because it rains and they did not take an umbrella than they are about taking an umbrella needlessly. Consequently, they may get unhappier at the

weather forecaster for a false forecast of dry weather than at a false forecast of rain. If so, the forecaster may well advance consumer happiness and thus his career by exhibiting a bias for forecasting rain. Indeed, we may conversely view the equivalent martingale measure of risk-neutral asset pricing as a consensus ‘wet bias’ negotiated through trading applied to the real-world probability space of outcomes.

Studies on weather forecast biases have typically focused on biases in the forecasts rather than in their updates. (Baars and Mass 2005) However, one can easily hypothesize similar incentives for biases in forecast updates. For example, if consumers of a forecast are unhappy about the forecast changing often, it may be a wise career move for the forecaster only to update his forecast once he is reasonably sure that he will not have to revise it back. One qualitative study found that at least for the special case of emergency situations, “once NWS forecasters have issued a forecast or warning, they generally prefer to update the product only if doing so will provide substantial new information to aid decision making,” *i.e.*, conservative bias in updates (Morss and Ralph 2007).

If forecasters are too aggressive or too conservative in updating forecasts, we should expect to see serial autocorrelations in the changes to their forecasts for the same event made over time. For example, if a forecast gets updated from 10 knots of wind to 15 knots, then if the forecaster is conservative, we might expect to see the next forecast for the same place and time to go to 17 knots. Of course, this view gets challenged if the forecaster simply does not update his forecast at all and prefers to leave it unchanged until the change in predictions is large enough that he has to include it. In that case, we would simply see the change as an innovation when it is finally included without seeing autocorrelation to a prior change that was too small to cause any update to be reflected in the forecast. Conversely, if the forecaster is too aggressive in his updates in the same scenario, we might expect the next forecast, as the forecast period draws nearer and more information gets revealed, to update his prediction back to 13 knots.

While the National Weather Service publishes some of its guidance for meteorologists writing TAFs as well as informal explanations, these do not seem to include any formal guidance on a wet bias or pricing kernel to apply to forecasts, *i.e.*, there seems to be no formal, published policy of over- or underweighting the likelihood of certain events. (“National Weather Service Instruction 10-813” 2024; Graf 2004)

It would also seem plausible for the forecaster to exhibit different degrees of conservatism and aggression in updating forecasts with good and bad news. We may call a bias that overresponds to bad news and underresponds to good news pessimistic; conversely, we may call a bias that underresponds to bad news and overresponds to good news optimistic. Of course, this classification only makes sense if updates to the forecast can reasonably be classified as good or bad news. Since there is a danger of confusion between ‘conservatism’ in the sense of being loathe to make an update and in the sense of being cautious and pessimistic, from here on, we will use the terms ‘underresponding’ for what the literature usually calls ‘conservative’ and ‘overresponding’ for the opposite.

We can then write down a matrix of four possible stylized biases in responding to changes in available information for a forecast where those changes can be classified as good or bad:

	Overresponding to good news	Underresponding to good news
Overresponding to bad news	Overresponding	Pessimistic
Underresponding to bad news	Optimistic	Underresponding

Table 1: Stylized biases of forecast updates

Our research question then becomes: Can we find evidence of bias in changes to Terminal Aerodrome Forecasts that manifest in autocorrelation of these changes for the same time and place? If so, which of our stylized biases does this bias belong to? Does the answer change for different variables? Does the answer change over time?

We should note that our question as posed does not directly answer anything about whether the forecasts of the TAFs come true. That would require looking at actual weather realizations, such as those reported in METARs. We can thus not say how autocorrelative bias in TAFs, if any, relates to the eventual realizations. Forecasters could, for example, be loath to include weather changes they have not previously forecast in a TAF, even if they are already reported in the METAR (and some pilots would claim anecdotal evidence for this being true). We can merely show whether knowledge of the history of the TAF predictions for a given time and place adds any information to what the final TAF prediction will likely look like, whether or not that actually corresponds to the weather realization.

2 Analysis

The software used to download, parse, process, and analyze the TAFs and generate this article is available at [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14954562](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14954562).

2.1 Data acquisition

We ran our analysis for the 713 aerodromes for which the National Weather Service published TAFs at the end of 2024. We built a downloader to obtain these TAFs from [Iowa State University's Iowa Environmental Mesonet](https://www.iowaenvironmental.org/) archive and made a data set from 1997 through 2024 available at [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14954564](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14954564). The United States changed its TAF format and the forecast range on 5 November 2008. (“Service Change Notice 08-46” 2008) In order

to avoid a break in our data set from this change, we limit our analysis to the years from 2010 through 2024.

We parsed 20,979,820 TAFs and encountered 25,207 errors. By the structure of our error reporting, one TAF may generate more than one error. Inspection of the error logs of unparsable TAFs shows that the problems are indeed with the TAFs or with their transmission and storage before we obtained them. With an error rate this low, we did not attempt to engage in any further cleanup of TAFs with syntax errors and felt it safer to exclude these from our analysis.

We also did not consider TEMPO and PROB elements in TAFs. PROB groups are not used for the first nine hours of a forecast and, after that, only for thunderstorm events. (“Advisory Circular 00-45H: Aviation Weather Services” 2016) This rule may introduce some reversionary tendencies since the PROB group has to disappear once it moves into the first nine hours, and since the PROB group is only used as a PROB30, it should more often than not be resolved into being taken out of the forecast. TEMPO groups are for events that cover less than half of their forecast period and for less than one hour. Since we structured our analysis in hourly intervals, we felt it safest to leave them out as well.

2.2 Variables considered

For our analyses, we parsed the TAFs we obtained and looked at the most pertinent (approximately, since they are reported as integers with rounding) continuous variables for flight/no flight decisions:

Wind speed without gusts in knots

Wind speed with gusts in knots; the gust speed if given, otherwise the wind speed

Gust spread in knots

Wind speed directional in knots, the northerly and easterly components of the wind speed

Lowest cloud layer in feet, the lowest cloud layer of any extent, taking clear skies as 18,000 feet

Ceiling in feet, the lowest cloud layer that is at least broken, taking clear skies as 18,000 feet

Visibility in statute miles, with a maximum value of 6 miles for unobstructed visibility

Other variables may certainly be important, including binary ones like the forecast presence of thunderstorms or cumulonimbus clouds, but we hope that these continuous variables will give us a good data set from which to analyze biases in forecast changes.

We show a detailed analysis of those data, both summaries and autocorrelations of changes, in their original units in section 5.

2.3 Quality transformation

In order to evaluate for optimistic and pessimistic biases, we need to say what a good or a bad value is for the variables in question. What different flight operations consider acceptable depends, of course, on factors such as the aircraft involved, whether the flight is conducted under visual or instrument flight rules, terrain, the alignment of available runways against the wind, *etc.* The goodness of a variable also need not be a monotonic function of its value. For example, some headwind is advantageous for a takeoff or landing. However, crosswinds and tailwinds are not. For simplicity, we treat the goodness of wind as monotonic and say that less wind is better. For cloud layers and visibility, larger distances are, of course, better, so for these variables, it is easy.

We then transform our variables by sigmoid curves as follows:

Wind speed, with and without gusts: Goodness of 1.00 for calm wind, 0.82 for 10 knots, 0.45 for 20 knots, 0.15 for 30 knots, and 0 for infinite wind.

Gust spread: Goodness of 1.00 for no gusts, 0.78 for 5 knots gust spread, 0.39 for 10 knots gust spread, 0.12 for 15 knots gust spread, and 0 for infinite gust spread.

Cloud layers, lowest and ceiling We apply the sigmoid curve to the square root of the layer's base altitude, giving a goodness of 0.00 for clouds to the ground, 0.13 for clouds at 500 feet, 0.29 for clouds at 1000 feet, 0.81 for clouds at 3000 feet, and 1.00 for clear skies.

Visibility We apply the sigmoid curve to the square root of visibility, giving a goodness of 0.00 for no visibility, 0.21 for 0.5 statute miles, 0.33 for 1 statute mile, 0.66 for 3 statute miles, and 1.00 for unlimited visibility.

We do not assign a goodness to directional wind speed as that would depend on the alignment of available runways (which is non-random since they tend to be aligned with prevailing wind, if possible).

The choice of these particular mappings is certainly somewhat arbitrary and much depends on the kind of flight operation, equipment, pilot experience, time, place, *etc.*, but they should give a somewhat intuitive and reasonable mapping of different observations on a scale between horrible and perfect. After all, the TAFs are not written for one specific flight operation but for general use for everyone between a powered parachute and a cargo 747. At any rate, we shall see patterns that appear robust to some amount of rescaling of these mappings.

2.4 First differences

We divide each TAF into hourly predictions for its prediction range. This will give us a number of predictions for each aerodrome and each hour. For all but the first and last of these predictions, we form triplets for each variable comprising the previously predicted value, the currently predicted value, and the value of the prediction in the final TAF issued for the hour in question.

We then take the first differences from the previous TAF to the current TAF and from the current TAF to the final TAF issued. The correlations between these first differences will inform us of the autocorrelations in changes of TAF predictions for the variables in question, transformed into goodness values to make them comparable.

Overall, this gives us 327,554,695 observations of pairs of changes in TAFs for a given hour for each variable, or 1,965,328,170 pairs of changes overall. Since most predictions span more than an hour, these observations are not independent (and, of course, even when the prediction changes between two hours are different, the predictions for these hours come out of the same forecasting process). Over all variables, 416,280,763 records involve a non-zero change between the previous and the current predictions.

3 Results

We can now examine the changes in the TAFs. We show a box plot with quartiles of changes to the final TAF after a prediction in a TAF for a given time and place has changed by a certain amount of goodness:

Figure 1: Autocorrelation of changes in predicted goodness of weather conditions

We can see that there clearly is a reversionary tendency in changes in TAFs. If forecasters make a change to a TAF, they tend to overrespond to new information and are likely to back out some of their changes in a later TAF. (The forecaster is an abstraction here. With them working in shifts, successive updates need not be made by the same person.) As a first approximation, for quite a few variables, the second and third quartiles of the changes seem to fall between the change remaining as is in the final TAF and the change getting fully backed out in the final TAF.

The autocorrelations appear asymmetric, however. Except for the lowest cloud base, the tendency of overreaction appears much stronger for worsening predictions than for improving ones. We can quantify this by a regression of the change to final against the change from the previous prediction:

Variable	Reversion of improvements	Reversion of deteriorations
clouds_ceiling	0.24	0.50
clouds_lowest_base	0.33	0.38
visibility	0.15	0.58
wind_gust_spread	0.24	0.54
wind_speed	0.24	0.49
wind_speed_with_gust	0.25	0.49

Table 2: Coefficients of reversion of changes in predicted goodness by variable

(We intentionally do not show p -values as rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no trace of autocorrelation in hundreds of millions of data points would be of very little interest and certainly not mean anything “significant.” The quantiles shown in Figure 1 seem much more informative to us as to whether the effect is worthwhile to consider.)

Thus changes in predictions exhibit a mixture of a pessimistic and an overreacting bias. Forecasters overreact when they adjust forecasts, but while they overreact strongly to worsening predictions, they overreact more mildly to improving predictions.

For visibility, the variable where forecasters are most pessimistic in their updates, this is so much so that we can expect improvements in prediction to last essentially unchanged into the final TAF, whereas worsenings will be backed out by two thirds on average. The base of the lowest cloud layer may be an exception to this rule where forecasters are much less pessimistic than for other variables, although they are still overresponding.

The degree of pessimism we are seeing may be connected to the potential of a variable to make pilots’ lives really sour, especially for large, commercial aviation. We see the least degree of pessimism in the base of the lowest cloud layer, a variable of relatively little importance to large flight operations, although pilots of small aircraft operating under visual flight rules and not wanting to get caught above the clouds or having to maneuver around them may care about it. We see the greatest degree of pessimism in visibility, where recreational flying might accept nothing worse than a very good prediction, while visibility declining to small values can make flying difficult or impossible even for the best-equipped aircraft and aerodromes.

If forecast biases are unintentional, one often sees them reducing over time. If they are intentional and serve a purpose, however, they may persist over time, even as users become conscious of them and computer models improve. We can thus look at the development of reversionary tendencies in changes to TAFs over time:

Figure 2: Reversion coefficients of changes in predicted goodness of weather conditions over time

It appears that the reversionary tendencies of forecasts have remained largely unchanged over a decade and a half. This suggests that they may be an intentional behavior by forecasters, not an artifact of computer models or unintentional bias.

We may finally ask whether reversionary tendencies might be more pronounced at certain places than others.

For worsening predictions, we see some tendencies different weather patterns might explain, but also some where that is at first glance hard to believe. In particular, there is a curious effect that worsening predictions in Wyoming seem to be significantly less likely to get reversed than in Montana or Colorado. The Rocky Mountains of Colorado form an island of pessimism with worsening predictions that are very likely to revert, whereas the equally treacherous skiing mountains around Lake Tahoe show very low reversion of worsening forecasts.

Reversion of Worsened Forecasts by Aerodrome

Figure 3: Reversion of worsened forecasts by aerodrome

For reversions of improvements in predictions, a cluster of optimism around Boston stands out, where improvements in predictions are much more likely to get reversed than in nearby New York City:

Reversion of Improved Forecasts by Aerodrome

Figure 4: Reversion of improved forecasts by aerodrome

4 Conclusion

It appears that there is indeed autocorrelation in changes to TAFs. Hence, a pilot can glean additional information by not only looking at the most current TAF for the time and place he wants to fly but also at previously issued TAFs for the same time and place. If the prediction worsened, there are grounds for hope that this worsening will be reversed in the final TAF before he goes flying. If the prediction improved, there are grounds for hope that the improvement will mostly hold, though it is not very likely to be improved further.

While TAFs have some power of their own, in particular concerning flights under instruments rules being allowed to take off, what matters most, of course, is not what the final TAF issued for a place and time looks like but how the weather actually turns out. From the interesting patterns we have seen in the evolution of the forecasts, the relationship between that evolution and eventual weather realizations might be a fertile field for another study.

5 Detailed Data Analysis

5.1 Wind speed without gusts

5.1.1 Summary statistics

Histogram

Wind speeds are forecast at an average of 7.9 knots.

Figure 5: Histogram of wind speeds

Extreme values

For wind speeds exceeding 10 knots, we see an exponential decay in their frequency of being forecast, albeit with a distinct clustering around round numbers. However, that relationship breaks down for the very small number of predictions exceeding 50 knots.

Figure 6: Histogram of wind speeds, log scale

By aerodrome

We see the well-known wind corridor from the Dakotas to West Texas:

Average Wind Forecast Speed by Aerodrome

Figure 7: Average wind forecast speed by aerodrome

The windiest airports, by prediction, are:

Aerodrome	Name	Average wind, knots
PACD	COLD BAY	14.9
PASN	SAINT PAUL ISLAND (ASOS)	14.4
KLVM	LIVINGSTON/MISSION	14.2
KRWL	RAWLINS MUNICIPAL	12.9
KAMA	AMARILLO ARPT(AWOS)	12.5
KCSM	CLINTON-SHERMAN	12.2

Table 3: Aerodromes with the highest predicted average wind speeds

5.1.2 Autocorrelation

Overall

Reductions in predicted wind speeds do not tend to get revised, but increases mostly get revised:

Figure 8: Changes in predicted wind speed *vs.* final prediction

We see a significantly larger effect size for the reversion of increases in predicted wind speeds with a reversion coefficient of 0.445 than for decreases with a coefficient of 0.284.

By year

It appears that there is no significant change in autocorrelation patterns over the years:

Figure 9: Changes in predicted wind speed *vs.* final prediction by year

By aerodrome

We break down the tendency of changes in predicted wind speed to revert by aerodrome. We see some geographic clusters, though their meaning is not immediately obvious.

Reversion of Increases in Predicted Wind Speed

Figure 10: Reversion of increases in predicted wind speed by aerodrome

Reversion of Decreases in Predicted Wind Speed

Figure 11: Reversion of decreases in predicted wind speed by aerodrome

5.2 Wind speed with gusts

5.2.1 Summary statistics

Histogram

Wind speeds with gust are forecast at an average of 9.3 knots.

We see an interesting distribution of wind speeds with gust with the typical exponential decay interrupted between 13 and 25 knots, presumably as a consequence of gust only being included above a threshold, then proceeding as expected from 25 knots to 70 knots, and ceasing there:

Figure 13: Histogram of wind speeds with gust

Extreme values

Figure 14: Histogram of wind speeds with gust, log scale

By aerodrome

The geographical distribution is as expected.

Average Wind Forecast Speed with Gust by Aerodrome

Figure 15: Average wind forecast speed with gust by aerodrome

The windiest airports for winds including gusts, by prediction, are:

Aerodrome	Name	Average wind with gust, knots
PACD	COLD BAY	18.7
KLVM	LIVINGSTON/MISSION	18.4
PASN	SAINT PAUL ISLAND (ASOS)	17.5
KRWL	RAWLINS MUNICIPAL	16.8
PHOG	KAHULUI	15.3
PADU	DUTCH HARBOR	15.1

Table 4: Aerodromes with the highest predicted average wind speeds with gust

5.2.2 Autocorrelation

Overall

Reductions in predicted wind speeds do not tend to get revised much, but increases mostly get revised:

Figure 16: Changes in predicted wind speed *vs.* final prediction

We see a significantly larger effect size for the reversion of increases in predicted wind speeds with gust with a reversion coefficient of 0.477 than for decreases with a coefficient of 0.261.

By year

It appears that there is no significant change in autocorrelation patterns over the years:

Figure 17: Changes in predicted wind speed with gust *vs.* final prediction by year

By aerodrome

There are some regional clusters for reversionary tendencies in predicted wind speed with gust, but their meaning is not immediately obvious.

Reversion of Increases in Predicted Wind Speed with Gust

Figure 18: Reversion of increases in predicted wind speed with gust by aerodrome

Reversion of Decreases in Predicted Wind Speed with Gust

Figure 19: Reversion of decreases in predicted wind speed by aerodrome

Reversion of predicted increases vs. decreases

We do not see much correlation between reversionary tendencies for increases and decreases in predicted wind speed with gust.

Reversion of Predicted Decrease vs. Increase of Wind Speed with Gust

Figure 20: Reversion of predicted decrease vs. increase of wind speed with gust by aerodrome

5.3 Wind speed directional

5.3.1 Summary statistics

Northerly and easterly wind components are forecast at an average of 5.4 knots. Patterns are as for wind speed:

Figure 21: Histogram of wind speed components

Figure 22: Histogram of wind speed components, log scale

5.3.2 Autocorrelation

Overall

Once we take wind direction into account and look at northerly and easterly components of wind speed, the pattern we have seen above of a distinction between increases and decreases in wind speed largely disappears and becomes more symmetrical. This is to be expected as directional wind speed has a sign.

Figure 23: Changes in predicted wind speed component *vs.* final prediction

The reversionary tendency remains with a reversion coefficient of 0.445.

5.4 Gust spread

5.4.1 Summary statistics

Histogram

Gust spreads are forecast at an average of 1.4 knots. Of course, this is an understatement since gusts are only reported when they are significant. For predictions including gust larger than zero, the mean gust spread is 8.8 knots.

The distribution is as follows:

Figure 24: Histogram of gust spreads

Extreme values

Again, we see an exponential decline of the frequency of the prediction of extreme values with the round value of 30 knots being an attractor:

Figure 25: Histogram of gust spread, log scale

By aerodrome

The geographical distribution shows little predicted gust on the Pacific coast, other than in Alaska and Hawaii, and in the Southeast:

Average Forecast Gust Spread by Aerodrome

Figure 26: Average forecast gust spread by aerodrome

The gustiest airports are:

Aerodrome	Name	Average gust spread, knots
KLVM	LIVINGSTON/MISSION	4.2
KRWL	RAWLINS MUNICIPAL	3.9
PACD	COLD BAY	3.8
PADU	DUTCH HARBOR	3.7
PAGY	SKAGWAY	3.6
PHMK	MOLOKAI_(ASOS)	3.6

Table 5: Aerodromes with the highest predicted average gust spread

5.4.2 Autocorrelation

Overall

Reductions in predicted gust spreads do not tend to get revised, but increases mostly get revised at least partially.

Figure 27: Changes in predicted gust spread *vs.* final prediction

We see a significantly larger effect size for the reversion of increases in predicted gust spreads with a reversion coefficient of 0.531 than for decreases with a coefficient of 0.24.

By year

It appears that there is no significant change in autocorrelation patterns over the years:

Figure 28: Changes in predicted gust spread *vs.* final prediction by year

By aerodrome

There are some regional clusters for reversionary tendencies in predicted gust spread, but their meaning is not immediately obvious.

Reversion of Increases in Predicted Gust Spread

Figure 29: Reversion of increases in predicted gust spread by aerodrome

Reversion of Decreases in Predicted Gust Spread

Figure 30: Reversion of decreases in predicted gust spread by aerodrome

Reversion of predicted increases vs. decreases

We see some correlation between reversionary tendencies for increases and decreases in predicted gust spreads.

Reversion of Predicted Decrease vs. Increase of Gust Spread by Aerodrome

Figure 31: Reversion of predicted decrease vs. increase of gust spread by aerodrome

5.5 Lowest cloud layer

5.5.1 Summary statistics

For the base of the lowest cloud layer, we see a mode for no clouds below 18,000 feet, which we show as 18,000 even for clear skies. Below that, we see a decline of prediction frequency with increasing altitude, with peaks at the round numbers of 10,000 feet and 15,000 feet.

Figure 32: Histogram of lowest cloud layer base

In the geographic distribution, we are seeing a distinct cluster of few low clouds in the sunny Southwest. We are showing the median instead of the average since the top value of 18,000 feet, which is also taken for clear skies, is an arbitrary choice.

Median Lowest Cloud Layer Base by Aerodrome

Figure 33: Median lowest cloud layer base by aerodrome

5.5.2 Autocorrelation

Overall

Since a change of a cloud layer from 10,000 feet to 9,500 feet clearly is not the same as a change from 1,000 feet to 500 feet, we look at changes in the square root of the altitude of the lowest cloud layer, taking clear skies or anything above 18,000 feet AGL as 18,000 feet.

Predicted changes in cloud layer on the median do not tend to get revised, but if they do get revised it is most often a reversion, whether for predicted increases or decreases:

Figure 34: Changes in predicted lowest cloud layer *vs.* final prediction

We see similar effect sizes for the reversion of increases and decreases of predicted lowest cloud layer with a reversion coefficient of 0.385 for increases and 0.349 for decreases.

By year

It appears that there is no significant change in autocorrelation patterns over the years:

Figure 35: Changes in predicted lowest cloud layer *vs.* final prediction by year

By aerodrome

We break down the tendency of changes in predicted visibility to revert by aerodrome. There is an interesting West-to-East gradient in reversion of increases:

Reversion of Increases in Predicted Lowest Cloud Layer

Figure 36: Reversion of increases in lowest cloud layer by aerodrome

For reversion of decreases, Florida and the Gulf Coast, together with Wyoming, form an interesting cluster of lower tendency to revert:

Reversion of Decreases in Predicted Lowest Cloud Layer

Figure 37: Reversion of decreases in predicted lowest cloud layer by aerodrome

5.6 Ceiling

5.6.1 Summary statistics

For the ceiling, the pattern from the lowest cloud base repeats:

Figure 39: Histogram of ceilings

Median Ceiling by Aerodrome

Figure 40: Median ceiling by aerodrome

5.6.2 Autocorrelation

Overall

Since a change of a cloud layer from 10,000 feet to 9,500 feet clearly is not the same as a change from 1,000 feet to 500 feet, we look at changes in the square root of the altitude of the ceiling, taking clear skies or anything above 18,000 feet AGL as 18,000 feet.

Predicted changes in ceiling on the median do not tend to get revised, but if they do get revised, it is most often a reversion, whether for predicted increases or decreases:

Figure 41: Changes in predicted ceiling *vs.* final prediction

For the ceiling, different from the lowest layer, we see somewhat of a tendency for decreases to revert more than increases do, with a reversion coefficient of 0.324 for increases and 0.435 for decreases.

By year

It appears that there is no significant change in autocorrelation patterns over the years:

Figure 42: Changes in predicted ceiling *vs.* final prediction by year

By aerodrome

We break down the tendency of changes in predicted ceiling to revert by aerodrome. In Florida, metropolitan California, West Texas, and Oklahoma we see clusters of an unusually low tendency of increases in predicted ceilings to revert:

Reversion of Increases in Predicted Ceiling

Figure 43: Reversion of increases in predicted ceiling by aerodrome

For reversion of decreases, we see a particular tendency for reversion in Dixieland and California:

Reversion of Decreases in Predicted Ceiling

Figure 44: Reversion of decreases in predicted ceiling by aerodrome

5.7 Visibility

5.7.1 Summary statistics

For visibility, six statute miles or better is by far the most predicted value:

Figure 46: Histogram of visibility

In the geographic distribution, we are seeing good visibility out West.

Mean Visibility by Aerodrome

Figure 47: Mean visibility by aerodrome

The airports with the best visibility, by prediction (keeping in mind that the scale maxes out at 6, but not using the median since that would be just 6 for most aerodromes), are:

Aerodrome	Name	Average visibility, sm
KEED	NEEDLES AIRPORT	5.9965
KLAS	LAS VEGAS - HARRY REID INTL	5.9953
KPHX	PHOENIX/SKY HARBOR	5.9941
KIFP	BULL HEAD CITY	5.9936
KVGT	NORTH LAS VEGAS	5.9933
KDUG	DOUGLAS BISBEE INTL	5.9926

Table 6: Aerodromes with the highest predicted visibility

The two airports in the contiguous United States with the lowest predicted visibility are both directly on the Pacific coast:

Aerodrome	Name	Average visibility, sm
PASC	DEADHORSE (ASOS)	4.3450
PABR	BARROW/POST-ROGERS (ASOS)	4.4337
PASN	SAINT PAUL ISLAND (ASOS)	4.5530
PAQT	NUIQSUT (ASOS)	4.5723
KACV	ARCATA/EUREKA ARPT	4.8746
KCEC	CRESCENT CITY	4.8763

Table 7: Aerodromes with the lowest predicted visibility

5.7.2 Autocorrelation

Overall

Since a change of visibility from 5 miles to 4.5 miles clearly is not the same as a change from 1 mile to 0.5 miles, we look at changes in the square root of visibility.

Improvements in predicted visibility do not tend to get revised, but decreases mostly get revised:

Figure 48: Changes in predicted visibility *vs.* final prediction

We see a significantly larger effect size for the reversion of decreases in predicted visibility than for increases, with a reversion coefficient of 0.149 for increases and 0.582 for decreases.

By year

It appears that there is no significant change in autocorrelation patterns over the years:

Figure 49: Changes in predicted visibility *vs.* final prediction by year

By aerodrome

We break down the tendency of changes in predicted visibility to revert by aerodrome. Again, there are regional clusters whose meaning is not immediately obvious.

Reversion of Increases in Predicted Visibility

Figure 50: Reversion of increases in predicted visibility by aerodrome

Reversion of Decreases in Predicted Visibility

Figure 51: Reversion of decreases in predicted visibility by aerodrome

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